

Utilisation of internet-enabled devices for academic and religious purposes among Muslim undergraduates

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated utilisation of internet-enabled devices for academic and religious purposes among Muslim undergraduates in University of Ilorin, Nigeria. All Muslim students in the University constituted the population of the study, while only those in the Faculty of Arts were the target population. Meanwhile, 50 Muslim students were randomly selected from each of the seven departments which totaled 350 undergraduate Muslim students. The instrument used to collect data was researcher-designed questionnaire. Two research hypotheses were formulated and tested using inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics, at 0.05 level of significance. It was revealed from the findings of the study that utilisation of internet-enabled devices significantly related to Muslim students' religious practices and academic performance. Therefore, it was concluded that students should always ensure moderation in chit-chatting and use their internet-enabled devices for the purposes which would boost their academic performance and improve them spiritually.

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1. INTRODUCTION

It is imperative to note that, nowadays, internet-enabled devices play significant roles in education [1]. Thus, the high level of awareness of internet-enabled devices in this contemporary period among Nigerian students has attracted research attentions [2].

Furthermore, with the development of portability and functional coverage of technologies, as well as cost reduction of products and services, internet enabled devices are increasingly found in our daily activities. Mobile technologies are commonly used nowadays even in areas where schools, books and computers are available. Due to low price of these technologies, mobile phones in particular, even in impoverished areas in Nigeria can afford and know how to use mobile device [3]. Moreover, Park and Biddix [4] viewed that, in Nigeria, abuse of internet has been extensively common among tertiary institution students, instead of legally using them to enrich themselves academically and spiritually. Functionally, the use of internet enabled devices by students improves their contributions in the learning process and increases their curiosity [5]. Similarly, internet-enabled devices help students to get needed materials, critically meditate, creatively operate and effectively collaborate with other people in finding solutions to problems [6]. In the same vein, internet is a very important tool in education. The more students use it for academic purpose, the more they

are likely to enrich their knowledge [7]. In addition, Alshahrani, *et al.* [8] stated that the internet brought a number of good dimensions to lecturers and instructors and sometimes, negative change to learners. Corroborating this statement, Park [9] stated that, internet-enabled devices assist students in getting and keeping educative information, sharing ideas, participating in virtual lectures, conduct online studies and engaging in religious affairs. Wertheim [10] opined that internet-enabled devices are also a spiritual space because a lot religious activities could be carried out on them by students, regardless of their religion. Moreover, Chen and Fu [11] opined that the use internet-enabled gadgets could have positive effects on students' academic performance and their religious practices.

In another development, Amoke and Igwebuike [12] believed that internet-enabled devices have become a good asset in education and they assist students in getting information which help facilitate their effective learning and consequently enhance their performance. In this respect, Amoke and Igwebuike [12] further stated that it is necessary to deny the use of such devices in schools in order to have a better development of the hectic pace of contemporary life. Meanwhile, in tertiary institutions, mobile devices especially smart phones are criticised by lecturers in view of the problems they bring such as distraction while the lecture is in progress. The use of internet has reduced face-to-face social interaction among students. It is also shown that, in compare to past years, teenagers in the 2010s spend more time on electronic communication than in person interaction [13]. Moreover, Briz-Ponce, *et al.* [14] submitted that in tertiary institutions in Nigeria, many students do not under-utilise the internet-enabled devices for academic and religious purposes, but over-utilise them for social matters. On this note, Gerpott and Thomas [15] stressed that, on daily basis, many University students spend more time on Twitter, Facebook and the likes more than the sites which would engage them academically and spiritually [16].

Meanwhile, utilization of internet-enabled devices for academic and religious activities needs to be more encouraged among students of higher institutions of learning [17]. Jibrin, *et al.* [18] maintained found stressed that internet-enabled devices have strong positive influence on students' academic performance as well as their religion. Al-Hamdani [19] found that Muslim students rarely use their mobile phones to translate texts translation, checking of spellings and words. Many students prefer using their mobile phones for watching films, playing games and listening to music to carrying out their academic activities [16].

Moreso, internet-enabled devices, if properly utilised, could build students to become independent learners and active collaborators in problem solving [20]. Therefore, Oghenetega and Igere [21] stated that, internet has become a very significant gadget for enhancing academic performance of students, if properly utilised. Internet-enabled devices have improved the academic environment exposing students to unlimited information as well as affording them the opportunity to share their knowledge globally [22]. Contrarily, social networking grabs the attention of students and then diverts it towards chatting, cyber building, watching and sharing of pornographic videos and photos, among others which Nigerian university students may not be left out [23].

Meanwhile, lecturers in Nigerian Universities need to continually encourage their students to used internet-enabled expedients for their academics and religious practices [17]. Utilisation of internet-enabled devices such as handset, tablet, laptop, palmtop seem to come with some observed attitudinal problems among university students, particularly Muslim undergraduates in the Faculty of Arts, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. Also, some parents are insensitive to their children utilise the devices as the institution might not have any measure in place to control the usage. As a result of this, students might abuse the use of the devices by wasting much pleasure, time, energy, and resources, busy with not beneficial chatting.

Many studies have been carried out concerning the utilisation of internet-enabled devices among university students. For instance, Ezemenaka [24] examined usage and Impact of internet-enabled phones on academic concentration among University of Ibadan students, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that many students were of habit of chatting with their phones while lecture is being delivered in the class. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study had been carried out on utilisation of internet-enabled devices for academic and religious purposes among Muslim undergraduates in the Faculty of Arts, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. This is the gap which this study filled. The main purpose of this study was to examine utilisation of internet-enabled devices for academic and religious purposes among Muslim undergraduates, Faculty of Arts, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. Specifically, it investigated the relationship: 1) Between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' religious practices; and 2) Between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance.

The following research questions were raised for this study: 1) Is there any relationship between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' religious practices?; 2) Is there any relationship between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance?. The research questions, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study: 1) Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim

undergraduates' religious practice; and 2) There is no significant relationship between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted descriptive research design of survey type. The population of the study comprised all Muslim students in University of Ilorin in 2018/2019 academic session, while the target population were all Muslim students in the Faculty of Arts, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. Meanwhile, 50 Muslim students were randomly selected from each of the seven departments (Religions, Arabic language, English language, French language, Yoruba language, History and Performing Art) which totaled 350 Muslim students. A random sampling technique was used to select the sample. A researcher-designed questionnaire was used to gather information. The questionnaire contained sections A and B. Section contained items on the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates religious practices while section B covered items on the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance. Copies of the questionnaire were presented to four experts in educational research for validation. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted among Muslim undergraduates in two departments, University of Ilorin which were not part of the main sample. The two results of administration were compared using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Statistics in which coefficient of correlation of 0.78 was obtained. The result indicated that the instrument was reliable for the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypotheses one and two were tested using inferential statistics of Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation statistics. Table 1 shows the calculated r-value (.622), while the p-value (.000) is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' religious practices is rejected. It means that there was a significant relationship between internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' religious practices.

Table 1. Internet-enabled devices and muslim undergraduates' religious practices

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Cal r-value	p-value
Internet- Enabled Devices	350	3.09	1.06	166	.622	.000
Muslim Students' Religious Practice	350	4.72	.77			

*Significant P< .05

Table 2 shows the calculated r-value (.510), while p-value (.000) is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between the utilisation of internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance is rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance.

Table 2. Internet-enabled devices and muslim undergraduates' religious practices

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Cal r-value	p-value
Internet- Enabled Devices	350	3.09	1.06	166	.510	.000
Muslim Students' Religious Practice	350	4.05	1.81			

*Significant P< .05

3.1. Discussion

Based on the results of this findings, it was found that there was a significant relationship between internet enabled-devices and Muslim undergraduates' religious practices. The result of this findings tallies with the findings of Al-Hamdani [19] that Muslim students use mobiles to translate texts, check spellings, look for vocabulary, and access a dictionary in class. Although created as video- sharing service for all users, YouTube has become part of many academics' and students' lives.

The second finding revealed that there was a significant relationship between internet-enabled devices and Muslim undergraduates' academic performance. This finding is similar to the findings of Kuznekoff [25] that students who were allowed to text and tweet in class scored significantly lower grades and scored lower on recalling information and note-taking. Also, Uden [20] found that the internet enable devices motivate students towards effective learning thereby enhancing their academic performance.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that lecturers should always encourage their students to use the internet-enabled devices for learning more than social matters in order to boost their academic performance. Students should also constantly keep themselves abreast of using the devices for spiritually purposes in order to continually improve their Islamic knowledge which would rightly direct their affairs.

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